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Knowledge and Practice Regarding Hepatitis B Virus Infection among Barbers of South West District of Delhi: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Viral hepatitis is a leading cause of death globally, with rising mortality rate and it is increasingly acknowledged as a major public health issue in India. Inadequate wound care, unclean work environment, and poor disinfection can make barbers and customers more vulnerable to Blood-borne viral infections (BBVI). **Aims & Objectives:** This study aims to assess the knowledge and practice of barbers regarding HBV infection. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 300 barbers using multi-stage random sampling. Knowledge was assessed using structured knowledge interview schedule and practice was assessed using structured practice rating scale. **Results:** Majority (75%) of the barbers possess fair knowledge regarding Hepatitis B virus infection and 25% of them exhibit poor knowledge regarding Hepatitis B virus infection. Most (82%) of barbers having poor practice whereas 18% having average practice. **Conclusion:** The study implies that nurses can advocate for screening programs, vaccination campaigns, and education on safe practices to mitigate HBV infection burden.

Keywords: Hepatitis B virus infection, knowledge, practice, barbers

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Introduction

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection continues to pose a significant public health challenge globally. Almost two thirds of the world's cases of hepatitis B and C are found in Bangladesh, China, Ethiopia, India, Indonesia, Nigeria, Pakistan, the Philippines, the Russian Federation, and Vietnam. It is imperative that the ten countries achieve universal access to prevention, diagnosis, and treatment by 2025. Additionally, increased efforts in the African Region are necessary to put the global response back on track to meet the Sustainable Development Goals. According to WHO estimates, globally, an estimated 296 million people are chronic carriers of Hepatitis B. Regional differences in age-specific HBsAg sero-prevalence are notable. Approximately 50% of the world's population resides in highly endemic areas. Over the past ten years, as the population infected with HBV matures and makes up the majority of patients in certain areas, the prevalence of HBeAg-negative illness has been rising. Without appropriate intervention, the number of deaths from HBV infection will continue to climb, reaching a peak of 1.14 million deaths by 2034. Hepatocellular carcinoma and cirrhosis are uncommon in Asia and most other regions until the age of 35 to 40, at which point their rates skyrocket.

Barbers are in direct contact with blood and bodily fluids of their clients during shaving, haircuts, and other grooming services. If a customer is infected with HBV and there are breaches in infection control practices, there is a risk of getting this

infection. Understanding the prevalence and risk factors can help implement targeted interventions to reduce transmission rates, thus mitigating the public health burden of HBV. Barbers are at occupational risk of acquiring blood borne infections like HBV due to frequent exposure to sharp instruments and potential contact with blood. Investigating the sero-prevalence among barbers can provide insights into the occupational health hazards they face, allowing for vaccination programs and training on infection control practices to protect their health.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the knowledge and practice of barbers regarding Hepatitis B virus infection.
2. To find out the relationship between knowledge and practice of barbers regarding Hepatitis B virus infection.
3. To seek the association of knowledge and practice of barbers with selected socio-demographic variables:
 - Age
 - Religion
 - Marital Status
 - Educational Status
 - Monthly Personal Income
 - Work experience as barber

Data Collection Tools and Techniques

Data was collected using the tools, Structured Knowledge interview schedule and structured practice rating scale. The content validity of the tools was established by giving it to 15 experts from the field of Community Medicine, Transfusion Medicine, Microbiology and Community Health Nursing. The reliability of Structured Knowledge interview schedule (0.83) and Structured practice rating scale (0.85) was established by KR-20 & Cronbach alpha respectively.

Tools	Purpose	Technique
Tool I: Structured Knowledge interview schedule	To assess the knowledge of barbers regarding HBV infection	Interviewing
Tool II: Structured practice rating scale	To assess the practice of barbers regarding HBV infection	Interviewing

Sample Size: 300 obtained from the Raosoft sample size calculator software

Raosoft	Percent
Margin of error can you accept	5.62
Confidence level	95.0
Population size (Use 20,000 if not known)	20.0
Response distribution	50.0
Recommended sample size	300

Sampling Technique: For the present study the multi-stage random sampling technique was used for selecting barbershops and barbers.

Stage I- Two sub-divisional areas of South-West district of Delhi were randomly selected through lottery method (i.e, Kapashera and Najafgarh sub-divisions were randomly selected from the three administrative sub-divisional areas of South-West district of Delhi).

Stage II- Further 10 areas of these two subdivisions were randomly selected.

Kapashera Subdivision: Kapashera, Samalkha, Bijwasan, Nangal Dewat, Rangpuri, Mahipalpur, Gadaipur, Aya Nagar, Satbari and Fatehpur Beri.

Najafgarh Subdivision: Najafgarh, Dichaon Kalan, Goela Dairy, Ghumanhera, Najafgarh Enclave, Prem Nagar, Roshan Garden, Chhawla, Jafarpur Kalan and Roshanpura.

Stage III- All barbers who are willing to participate and working in these 10 areas of barbershops has been selected.

Materials and Methods

After obtaining formal administrative approval from appropriate authority the final study was conducted from 24th January 2024 to 19th February 2024 in South-west district of Delhi. Through multi-stage random sampling technique 300 barbers were selected. Self-introduction and establishment of a rapport with participants were done. The researcher explained the nature, purpose and their expected participation in the study. Written consent has been taken from all the participants. The subjects were assured confidentiality of their responses. Data collection was done through face-to-face interview. Then individual barber was interviewed using Structured Knowledge interview schedule and Structured practice rating scale to assess their knowledge and practice regarding HBV infection. Time taken for the completion of each interview was 30-35 minutes. The data obtained were analysed and interpreted using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results

Majority (59.67%) of the barbers were in the age group 18-28 years, most (54.67%) of them were unmarried. Majority (36%) of barbers were having high school as educational qualification. 44.67% of barbers were having monthly personal income between Rs.15,001- 20,000 and were belongs to Islam religion. Maximum (46.67%) of sample were residing in urban area. Most (35.33%) of the barbers were having work experience above 12 years. Majority (80%) of barbers didn't undergo any vocational training to work as barber. 32.67% of barbers considering this job as ancestral job. Maximum (69.38%) of barbershops were located in the urban area whereas 3.4% were located in rural area and 11.56% were in roadside.

Maximum (82%) of barbers were not having previous knowledge on HBV infection. Most (80.66%) of the barbers don't know their previous testing of HBsAg. Maximum (53.84%) of the samples don't know the reason for testing and 30.76% done HBsAg screening before as a pre-operative requirement. Majority (54.0%) of the barbers were having a normal weight (BMI 18.5-23) whereas 25.66% were having a overweight BMI (23.1-27.5).

Majority (75%) of the barbers possesses fair knowledge regarding Hepatitis B virus infection and 25% of them exhibit poor knowledge regarding Hepatitis B virus infection. Mean ± SD of knowledge score was 11.25±2.69 and median was 12. Knowledge scores were found to be lowest in the area of prevention (mean score 34.12%) followed by 44.6% in the area of definition, causes and risk factors. Mode of transmission and Signs & Symptoms were ranked I & II respectively.

Table-1: Frequency and percentage distribution of barbers according to their knowledge scores regarding Hepatitis B infection

Knowledge Score Category	No.	%
Poor (Score 0-8)	75	25
Fair (Score 9-16)	225	75
Good (Score 17-25)	-	-
N=300 Maximum Score- 25		

Table-2: Mean, Median and Standard Deviation of Knowledge Scores of Barbers Regarding Hepatitis B Infection

Variable	Mean ± SD	Median
Knowledge score	11.25 ± 2.69	12

Most (82%) of barbers are having poor practice whereas 18% having average practice. Data shows that, the mean practice score is 41.38, median practice score (40) suggesting that the overall practice of the barbers regarding HBV infection was poor. The standard deviation of the practice scores ± 3.86 , shows a homogenous group in terms of practice.

Rank order scoring of practice area reveals that lowest (24.6%) mean score was in the area of use of PPE followed by 41% in the area of disinfection practice. It suggests that the barbers are not following the ideal and standard practices to prevent the transmission of Hepatitis B infection.

Table- 3: Frequency & Percentage Distribution of Barbers according to their Practice Scores Regarding Hepatitis B Infection (N=300)

Practice Score		No.	%
Category	Poor (Score-25-39)	246	82.0
	Average (Score 40-55)	54	18.0
	Good (Score 56-75)	-	-
Maximum Score = 75			

Table- 4: Mean, Median and Standard Deviation of Practice Scores of Barbers regarding Hepatitis B Infection (N=300)

Variable	Mean \pm SD	Median
Practice score	41.38 \pm 3.86	40
Maximum Possible Score = 75		

Table-5: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Barbers according to their Practice Scores regarding Hepatitis B Infection (N=300)

Variables	Always		Sometimes		Never		
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Use of personal protective equipment	Use of gloves during cutting/ shaving	-	-	18	6%	227	94
	Use of apron	106	35.33	161	53.67	33	11
	Cover cuts in hands while on job	63	21	211	70.33	26	8.67
	Collect shaved hair on bare hands	115	38.33	152	50.67	33	11
	Perform after shave massage with bare hand	163	54.33	102	34	35	11.67
Disinfection practice	Dip used instruments in a disinfectant solution	27	9	41	13.66	232	77.33
	Clean alum bar with a disinfectant after shaving/trimming	6	2	92	30.66	202	67.33
	Wash hands before every cutting/ shaving	8	2.67	100	33.33	192	64
	Wash hands after every cutting/ shaving	101	33.67	163	54.33	36	1.2
	Disinfect instruments after use in hypochlorite solution for 30 minutes	0	0	0	0	0	0
Post-exposure management	Wash the area with water	182	60.67	99	33	19	6.33
	Wash the area with soap & water	63	21	195	65	42	14
	Wash the area with Dettol	115	38.33	182	60.67	3	1
	Ignore/do nothing	3	1	180	60	117	39
	Put injured/area in mouth	-	-	186	62	114	38
	Squeeze the area	-	-	116	38.67	184	61.33
	Use Bleach/ Chlorine/ Alcohol/ Betadine or any antiseptic	3	1	169	56.33	128	42.67
	Use of alum bar	180	60	90	30	30	10
Consult a doctor	-	-	-	-	300	100	
Disposal of waste	Dispose used blades separately in a container	34	11.33	100	33.33	162	55.44
	Use bare hand to dispose the waste generated	282	94	18	6	-	-
	Use gloves to dispose blood-stained waste	16	5.3	2	.66	282	94
Use of items/ instruments	Use separate towel for each cutting/shaving	74	24.67	73	24.33	153	51
	Use separate blade for each shaving	288	96	2	0.67	10	0.33
	Use electric trimmers/shavers	171	57	82	27.33	47	15.67

Majority of participants (88%) collected shaved hair on bare hands, 88.33% reported performing after-shave massage with bare hands and 79% reported not covering cuts in their hands while on the job. Most of the participants (77.33%) exhibited poor disinfection practice like 67.33% do not cleaned used alum bars with a disinfectant, 64% reported not washing hands before

every cutting/shaving. However, 33.67% of barbers were performed hand washing after each cutting/shaving. None of the participants reported disinfecting used instruments in a hypochlorite solution. Majority of participants (99%) reported ignoring or doing nothing after exposure. Only 24.67% of participants reported using a separate towel for each cutting/shaving. 57% of participants prefer to use electric shavers/trimmers. Hence the above data reveals poor practices among barbers which pause them potential for transmission of HBV infection among them and their clients & families.

The data presented in table 8 shows a very weak positive correlation between the knowledge scores and the practice scores ($r = 0.12$) of the barbers regarding Hepatitis B virus infection which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis H01 was rejected and the research hypothesis H1 was accepted.

Table-6: Karl Pearson Co-efficient of Correlation 'r' value Showing Relationship between Knowledge Score & Practice Score of Barbers Regarding Hepatitis B Virus Infection (N=300)

Category	Mean ± SD	Coefficient of Correlation 'r'
Knowledge Scores	11.25 ± 2.69	0.12
Practice score	41.38 ± 3.86	
'r' value for df (298) 'r'= 0.06		

Table-7: Chi-Square values showing Association between Knowledge Scores with selected Socio-Demographic variables among Barbers (N=300)

Variables		Knowledge Score			df	χ^2 value	Critical value	Significant
		Good	Fair	Poor				
Age (years)	Less than 18 years	-	1	25	5	77.16	11.07	S*
	18-28 years	-	146	33				
	29-38 years	-	43	5				
	39-48 years	-	27	4				
	49-58 years	-	7	6				
Marital Status	Above 58 years	-	1	2	4	13.43	9.48	S*
	Unmarried	-	121	43				
	Married	-	104	32				
	Divorced	-	-	-				
	Widower	-	-	-				
Religion	Live-in relationship	-	-	-	2	26.63	5.99	S*
	Hindu	-	78	20				
	Christian	-	2	-				
Educational Status	Muslim	-	145	55	5	62.17	11.07	S*
	Illiterate	-	5	26				
	Primary School	-	36	20				
	Middle School	-	48	4				
	High School	-	101	7				
Monthly personal income	Intermediate School	-	23	18	4	57.84	9.48	S*
	Degree	-	12	-				
	Rs. 5,000- 10,000	-	2	15				
	Rs. 10,001- 15,000	-	77	30				
	Rs. 15,001- 20,000	-	110	24				
Work experience	Rs. 20,001- 25,000	-	30	5	4	64.61	9.48	S*
	Rs. 25,001- 30,000	-	6	1				
	6 months-3 years	-	4	40				
	4-6 years	-	44	11				
	7-9 years	-	57	9				
10-12 years	-	21	8					
More than 12 years	-	99	7					
*Significant at 0.05 level								

According to the data given in the above table the computed Chi Square value with selected variables like marital status (13.43), religion (26.63), education (62.17) monthly personal income (57.84), age (77.16) and work experience (64.61) were found to be statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that knowledge is dependent on age, work experience, marital status, religion, education and monthly personal income.

Table-8: Chi-Square values showing Association Between Practice Scores and Selected Socio-Demographic Variables among Barbers (N=300)

Variables		Practice Score			df	χ ² value	Critical value	NS/ S
		Good	Average	Poor				
Age (years)	Less than 18 years	-	-	26	5	86.27	11.07	S*
	18-28 years	-	39	140				
	29-38 years	-	8	40				
	39-48 years	-	4	27				
	49-58 years	-	3	10				
	Above 58 years	-	-	3				
Marital Status	Unmarried	-	34	130	4	15.37	9.48	S*
	Married	-	20	116				
	Divorced	-	-	-				
	Widower	-	-	-				
	Live-in relationship	-	-	-				
Religion	Hindu	-	20	78	2	29.41	5.99	S*
	Christian	-	-	2				
	Muslim	-	34	166				
Educational Status	Illiterate	-	2	29	5	72.38	11.07	S*
	Primary School	-	20	36				
	Middle School	-	12	40				
	High School	-	20	88				
	Intermediate School	-	-	-				
	Degree	-	-	-				
Monthly personal income	Rs.5,000- 10,000	-	7	10	4	78.72	9.48	S*
	Rs. 10,001- 15,000	-	27	80				
	Rs. 15,001- 20,000	-	-	134				
	Rs. 20,001- 25,000	-	18	17				
	Rs. 25,001- 30,000	-	2	5				
Work experience	6 months-3 years	-	12	32	4	71.11	9.48	S*
	4-6 years	-	15	40				
	7-9 years	-	6	60				
	10-12 years	-	10	19				
	More than 12 years	-	16	90				
*Significant at 0.05 level								

According to the data given in the above table the computed Chi Square value with selected variables like age (86.27), marital status (15.37), religion (29.41), educational status (72.38), work experience (71.11) & monthly personal income (78.72) were found to be statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, it indicates that practice of barbers regarding Hepatitis B virus infection was dependent on monthly personal income, age, religion, marital status, educational status and work experience.

Discussion

The present study indicates that, majority (75%) of the barbers possess fair knowledge regarding Hepatitis B virus infection whereas a notable proportion (25%) of the barbers exhibited poor knowledge, most (82%) of barbers were having poor practice score and 18% having average practice. Lowest (24.6%) mean practice score was in the area of use of PPEs followed by 41% in the area of disinfection practice. These results are consistent with the findings of the study conducted by Imtiaz Hussain et al. (2017)⁴ overall knowledge about HBV infection and its transmission was poor in 70% of barbers. 18% barbers know liver as the organ affected by HBV and 67% knew about its transmission by razors, 90% barbers used antiseptic solution after each client and only 13% had undergone screening tests for HBV infection.

A study conducted by N. Abbasi et al. (2014)⁵ to determine hepatitis B virus (HBV) prevalence among barbers and their knowledge, attitude and practices in a peri-urban district through interview method using a structured questionnaire showed a prevalence of HBV among barbers (2.1%) and knowledge on HBV and its transmission routes was poor.

In another study conducted by Zafar Fatmi et al. (2018)⁶ revealed barbers' knowledge on HBV and its transmission routes was poor. The overall performance on the knowledge and practice scales was poor compared to the attitude scale on which 80% of the barbers performed well.

Limitations

- The present study was limited to 300 barbers of Southwest District of Delhi that posing restriction to make a broader generalization.
- Study Samples were restricted to only one setting.
- The information collected from Barbers was based on their expressed responses. Participants might provide socially acceptable responses leading to potential underreporting of high-risk behaviours.
- The structured interview schedule and practice rating scale were developed as no standardized tools were available for assessment of barber's knowledge and practice regarding Hepatitis B virus infection.

Conclusion

The study underscores the importance of promoting awareness about HBV infection, risk factors and practices to prevent transmission of HBV infection. Majority of the barbers possess fair knowledge and a notable proportion exhibited poor knowledge regarding Hepatitis B virus infection. It suggests that the barbers lack good knowledge in all the areas however, the knowledge scores in the area of mode of Transmission and signs& symptoms and Diagnosis were found to be greater as compared to other areas. The data signifies the importance of proper awareness on standard precaution practices to minimize the transmission of Hepatitis B infection to barbers and their clients.

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